

Farming systems

Farmer performance in a ricebased farming system: differences between new and old systems

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We investigated farmers' performance in an area under a large irrigation project in the southern dry zone of Sri Lanka. The farming system is based on rice cultivation during the wet (maha) and dry (yala) seasons. The irrigation project concentrated on developing the existing fanning system and developing new land for cultivation. A network of irrigation channels was constructed in the newly developed area and institutional support for inputs was provided.

We conducted a field survey during Apr-May 1994. Rice farmers, 56 from the new area and 48 from the old area, were randomly selected. The farmers' technical efficiency was measured using Pingali's farmer performance index, which is the ratio of farmers' yield to the location-specific yield potential. The index explains the extent to which a farmer has exploited the yield potential. If the farmer performance index is less than 100, it means that he or she experiences an unexploited yield potential.

The potential yield in the project area is about 4.8 t/ha, based on yields from a series of farmer-managed on-farm experiments carried out for several seasons. Farmers exploited 75% of the yield potential with an average of 3.6 t/ha. Farmers' performance, however, differed in the two areas. Farmers in the new area had low performance compared with farmers in the old area. Only 7% of the farmers in the new area and 13% of the farmers in the old area reached the yield potential (see figure).

The main limitations in the new area were a lack of water, especially during the dry season, and problems with water distribution. Disparities were encountered with the field location and water distribution was uneven because some farmers extracted water through unauthorized means. Other constraints included soil problems, such as salinity: farmers' perceptions toward

Farmer performance index in two domains. Sri Lanka, 1994.

participating in farmer organizations; and damage by elephants to fields.

The managers of the project need to distribute the limited water in an effective manner, considering the existing constraints. Such an effort would help to increase the farmers' performance in the new area. ■

Farm machinery

Hand tools used for rice harvesting in South Sulawesi, Indonesia

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The *ani-ani* is a hand-held harvesting knife for cutting rice panicles. When farmers in Indonesia commonly planted traditional varieties, the *ani-ani* was predominantly used to prevent grain from falling off the panicles. When farmers started to plant different rice types and varieties, they found that the *ani-ani* was no longer efficient and switched to using unserrated sickles.

A study conducted at Sidenreng Rappang, a major rice-producing area in South Sulawesi, showed that farmers predominantly use the unserrated sickle, with some using the serrated sickle. A few still use the *ani-ani* (see table).

Farmers' preferences for using unserrated sickles were based only on their familiarity with the equipment. Like the

ani-ani, the unserrated sickle has low capacity and causes high grain losses. The serrated sickle is the most promising in terms of capacity compared with the unserrated sickle or *ani-ani*. The area harvested with the serrated sickle was significantly larger than the area harvested with the other tools in 1993 (see table).

The highest mean harvest capacity was 0.83 ha/sickle (assuming 1 person= 1 sickle) with the serrated sickle, which was 32.7 times higher than with the unserrated sickle, and 189 times higher than with the *ani-ani*. However, serrated sickles were available only in the subdistricts where rice is not harvested.

The serrated sickle is the recommended tool for harvesting rice in South Sulawesi because it is more efficient and incurs less harvesting losses than the unserrated sickle or *ani-ani*. ■

Number of harvesting tools and area harvested in Sidenreng Rappang District. ^a South Sulawesi, Indonesia. 1993

Location (subdistrict)	Harvesting tool					
	Unserrated sickle		Serrated sickle		Ani-ani	
	Units (no.)	Harvested area (ha)	Units (no.)	Harvested area (ha)	Units (no.)	Harvested area (ha)
Panca Lautang	13,349	-	1,444	-	1,193	-
Dua Pitue	16,847	310.3	3,009	4,514.0	-	-
Maritengngae	9,134	5,103.0	2,813	1,403.0	230	-
Watang Pulu	655	100.0	538	100.0	178	2.5
Baranti	192,188	200.0	538	750.0	617	5.0
Panca Rijang	6,226	311.3	445	250.0	182	3.0
Total	238,399	6,024.6	8,487	7,017.0	2,400	10.5

^a Source: Food Crops Extension Services. Sidenreng Rappang, 1994.